

SURVEILLANCE CARD Disease Y - Detection of new infectious agent causing disease in Livestock

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in livestock
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of new infectious agent causing disease (with potential of causing of Disease X in humans) in livestock
3	Target species and group	All livestock
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable/ to be defined/reported
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country
6	Age group	All
7	Sampling point and strategy	Livestock morbidity and mortality reported by farmers to livestock practitioners. Can be complemented by any other methods to monitor and detect increased in productive or reproductive failure, as long as practices to raise alarms, report and follow-up these alarms are set in place.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited
9	Sampling matrix	To be defined based on pathological findings
10	Type of disease indicators	Dead animals
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	No risk factors
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Complete diagnostic investigation. Following exclusion of known pathogens, additional diagnostic investigations using metagenomics, whole genome sequencing, etc.

14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Not applicable
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	All other livestock pathogens that cause morbidity and mortality
18	References	Not applicable
19	Additional comments	Note: It is important to assure a timely exchange and investigations of similar cases in other animal species and humans